

Synthesis of Some 2,6-Diamino-9-arylpurines, 2,6-Diamino-9-aryl-8-azapurines and Some Related 5-Phenylazopyrimidines

D. SEN and PURNENDU SENGUPTA

Department of Applied Chemistry, University College of Science and Technology, Calcutta-9

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Synthesis of some 2,6-diamino-9-arylpurines, 2,6-diamino-9-aryl-8-azapurines and 2,4-diamino-6-arylamino-5-phenylazopyrimidines have been reported. 9-Aryl-purines were prepared by the cyclization with formamide of appropriate 6-arylamino-2,4,5-triaminopyrimidine bisulphite. The 9-aryl-8-azapurines were prepared by the cyclization of the above 2,4,5-triaminopyrimidine bisulphites with nitrous acid. The 6-arylamino-2,4,5-triaminopyrimidine bisulphites were obtained by the reduction of the 2,4-diamino-5-nitroso-6-arylamino-pyrimidines with sodium hydrosulphite. The 5-phenylazopyrimidines were synthesized by the reaction of appropriate 2,4-diamino-6-arylamino-pyrimidines with benzenediazonium chloride. The assignment of structures of these 9-aryl-purines and 9-aryl-8-azapurines were based upon their lack of acidic character.

IT has been demonstrated that 2,6-diaminopurine exhibits significant antitumor activity¹ and inhibitory effect on the growth of certain bacteria, viruses and animal tissues²⁻⁶. It is also known that many tumors which incorporate guanine into DNA and RNA very poorly, utilize 2,6-diaminopurine as a nucleic acid guanine source with reasonable efficiency⁷. These facts prompted us to investigate the synthesis of some 9-arylsubstituted-2,6-diamino purines and of some related 8-azapurines, which as analogues of 2,6-diaminopurine nucleosides might exhibit anti-tumor and antimicrobial activity. We report in this paper the synthesis of some new compounds of the above types. Preliminary investigations have revealed that some of these compounds inhibit the growth of *S. faecalis* and behave as folic acid antagonists.

For the synthesis of 2,6-diamino-9-aryl-purine, we have used 2,4,5-triamino-6-arylamino-pyrimidine as the starting material (Compound II/Scheme I). This was cyclized by boiling its bisulphite salt in formamide. In this case there are two possible modes of cyclization :

- (1) that involving the 4- and 5-amino groups to produce 6-arylamino-purine, and
- (2) that involving 5-amino- and 6-arylamino groups to produce 9-aryl-purines.

While the 4-amino group was expected to be more reactive in cyclization reactions than the 6-arylamino group, the converse proved to be true in all cases studied previously. In all instances 2,6-diamino-9-aryl-purines were formed and not the isomeric 2-amino-6-arylamino-purines⁸⁻⁹. In our experiments also only the 9-aryl-purines were obtained. The presence of an aryl group at 9-position of the purine ring was proved by the purine's lack of solubility in base, since an unsubstituted imidazole ring should impart acidic characteristics to the compound.

We had thought of preparing the 9-aryl-2,6-diamino-purines (III) by the cyclization of 2,4-diamino-6-arylamino-5-formylaminopyrimidines with formamide. This procedure had to be abandoned because we could not prepare the required 2,4-diamino-6-arylamino-5-formylaminopyrimidines by the reductive formylation of the corresponding 5-nitroso compounds with zinc dust and formic acid following the method used by Pfeleiderer *et al.*¹⁰. We, therefore, prepared the 6-arylamino-2,4,5-triaminopyrimidines (II) by the reduction of 6-arylamino-2,4-diamino-5-nitrosopyrimidines (I) with sodium hydrosulphite. Attempts to prepare this compound (II) by the reduction of the corresponding 5-phenylazopyrimidines with sodium hydrosulphite were also unsuccessful. We did not make any attempt for purification of the compounds (II). They were cyclized directly with formamide to give the desired 2,6-diamino-9-aryl-purines (III).

Treatment of crude 6-arylamino-2,4,5-triaminopyrimidines (II) with sodium nitrite in acetic acid gave 2,6-diamino-9-aryl-8-azapurines [5,7-diamino-3-aryl-*v*-triazolo (*d*) pyrimidines] (IV). Treatment of compounds (II) with nitrous acid is expected to lead to the formation of 9-substituted-8-azapurines (IV) by ring closure between the 5-amino group and the 6-secondary amino group and not to the formation of the isomeric 6-substituted amino-8-azapurines by the alternative mode of ring closure. The structure (IV) has been ascribed as the product was insoluble in strong potassium hydroxide solution indicating the absence of an acidic hydrogen atom. An acidic hydrogen atom would be present if the 4- and 5-amino groups are both involved in the formation of the triazole ring. A similar treatment of 4,5-diamino-6-furfuryl aminopyrimidine with nitrous acid has been shown by Hull¹¹ to produce 7-amino-3-furfuryl-*v*-triazolo [*d*] pyrimidine.

The purines and azapurines are all crystalline solids melting with decomposition above 250°. These are insoluble in common organic solvents at room temperature. The compounds prepared and their characteristics are listed in Table 1.

It is also known that a number of pyrimidines having two amino groups at C₂ and C₄ positions and a bulky substituted amino group at C₆ position inhibit the growth of some microorganisms¹⁹⁻²⁰. We were, therefore, interested in studying the effect

TABLE I

Compound	R	Molecular formula	M.P. (colour)	Overall yield from compd. (I) %	Analysis %		Absorption	
					Found	Reqd.	λ_{max} (nm)	$\log \epsilon$
III	-H	C ₁₁ H ₉ IN ₆ , H ₂ O	282°(d)* (yellow crystal)	40	C : 36.20	35.7	215	4.34
					H : 3.02	3.0	250	4.29
					N : 22.03	22.7		
III	-OCH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₆ O	285°(d)** (white shining needle)	58	C : 56.35	56.25	220	4.51
					H : 4.95	4.68	280	4.16
					N : 32.19	32.81		
IV	-H	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₇ I	282°(d) (Brown Crystal)	45	C : 33.96	34.00	220	4.42
					H : 2.52	2.26	303	4.25
					N : 27.76	27.7		
IV	-OCH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₇ O	304°(d) (Light Pink Crystal)	39	C : 51.75	51.36	230	4.47
					H : 4.65	4.28	293	4.13
					N : 38.65	38.13		
IV	-CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₇	308°(d) (Pink crystal)	35	C : 54.48	54.77	225	4.54
					H : 4.78	4.56	298	4.21
					N : 40.90	40.66		

* M.P. of the hydrochloride 308°(d)

** M.P. of the hydrochloride 304°(d).

5-Arylazopyrimidines are often known to possess interesting biological properties. Several workers have synthesized a number of 5-arylazopyrimidines and found that many of them possess interesting antifolic, antimicrobial and antineoplastic properties¹²⁻¹⁹.

of introducing a phenylazo group in the 5-position of the above type of compounds on their biological properties. In the present paper we describe the synthesis of three such 5-phenylazo compounds (V).

Preliminary investigations have shown that the

5-phenylazo compounds inhibit the growth of *S. faecalis* and act as folic and antagonists.

The 5-phenylazopyrimidines (V) were prepared by the reaction of an appropriate 2,4-diamino-6-arylamino-pyrimidine with diazotised aniline. The coupling reaction was carried out at a temperature of 2°-5° and at slightly alkaline pH (pH 8-9). Proper maintenance of pH was found essential for the reaction.

The 5-phenylazo compounds are coloured crystalline compounds, insoluble in common organic solvents at room temperature. The compounds and their characteristics are indicated in Table 2. It can be

rapidly heating the block to about 20° below the actual melting point and then heating the block at the rate of ca 4°/min. All the melting points reported are "corrected".

In crystallisation, the term "alcohol" always refers to 95% (w/w) ethanol.

Absorption spectra of the compounds were determined in absolute alcohol in 1 cm. cell in the model DU Beckman Spectrophotometer.

For analysis the compounds were dried over phosphorus pentoxide at 110°/1 mm. for 16 hr.

General method for the preparation of 6-arylamino-2,4,5-triaminopyrimidine bisulfites (II) :

Thoroughly powdered 2,4-diamino-6-arylamino-5-nitrosopyrimidine²⁰ (Comd.I/0.01 mole) was suspended in 50 ml. of boiling water (the compound was moistened before use) and sodium hydrosulfite (0.04 mole) was slowly added with stirring to this hot suspension. The resulting mixture was boiled gently for 20-40 min. During addition and subsequent boiling the deeply coloured nitroso compound gradually changed to light yellow triamino compound. The mixture was then cooled to below 0° in the refrigerator for 3 hr. The solid separated was filtered off, washed with a little ice-cold water and dried overnight in the vacuum dessicator over silica gel. This crude compound was used directly for the next step without further purification.

TABLE 2*

Com- pound	R	Molecular formula	M.P. °(d) (colour)	Solvent for crystalliza- tion	Analysis %		Absorption	
					Found	Reqd.	λ_{max} (nm)	log ϵ
V	-I	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₇ I	258 (Yellow shining crystal)	alcohol ⁺⁺	C : 44.25 H : 3.2 N : 23.01	44.5 3.2 22.7	250 290 420	4.26 4.48 4.36
V	-OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₇ O	206 (Orange needles)	alcohol- water mixture ⁺	C : 61.26 H : 4.93 N : 29.39	60.9 5.07 29.25	245 280 320** 420	4.41 4.41 3.57 4.28
V	-CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₇	237 (Yellow needles)	alcohol- water mixture	C : 64.16 H : 5.67 N : 30.77	63.9 5.3 30.7	250 280 400	4.18 4.34 4.37

* The yield of the cryst. compd. in all cases were 80%.
 ** Very inconspicuous.
 + Can also be crystallised from glacial acetic acid.
 ++ 125 ml alcohol required for 1 g of the substance.

seen from the table that all the compounds absorb light in the 400-420 nm region, which accounts for their deep colours.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes on a copper block. Melting point of compounds that melted with decomposition was determined by

General method for the preparation of 2,6-diamino-9-arylpyrimines (III) :

The dry crude 2,4,5-triamino-6-arylamino pyrimidine bisulfite (II) (as obtained from previous experiment) was suspended in formamide (10 ml) and boiled gently under reflux for 30 min. As the refluxing started, the compound first went into solution and after 5 min a precipitate started appear-

ing. After the reaction was over, the reaction mixture was diluted with water (30 ml) and cooled overnight in the refrigerator. The crude product was filtered off, washed with water, dried at 80°. For purification it was crystallised as hydrochloride from 2(*N*) hydrochloric acid using norite.

To obtain the free base a small amount of the hydrochloride was dissolved in hot 2(*N*) hydrochloric acid and the free base was precipitated with excess of ammonium hydroxide.

*General method for the preparation of 2,6-diamino-9-aryl-8-azapurines [5,7-diamino-3-aryl-*v*-triazolo [*d*] pyrimidines] (IV):*

The crude 2,4,5-triamino-6-arylamino pyrimidine bisulfite (prepared as before from 0.008 mole nitroso pyrimidine) was dissolved in 150 ml (225 ml in case of 6-*p*-tolyl compound) of boiling water with the addition of 10–20 ml of glacial acetic acid. The solution was then heated on the steam bath and a solution of sodium nitrite (0.01 mole) in water (8 ml) was slowly added with stirring. On addition of sodium nitrite solution, a brown precipitate started appearing. Heating and stirring were continued for one more hour. The reaction mixture was cooled overnight in the refrigerator. The solid separated was collected by filtration, washed twice with water (2 × 10 ml) and dried at 80° for 2 hr. It was finally crystallised from *N,N*-dimethyl formamide—water mixture using charcoal.

General method for the preparation of 5-phenylazo-pyrimidines:

2,4-diamino-6-arylamino pyrimidine (0.004 mole) (three compounds were used—2,4-diamino-6-*p*-iodo-anilino pyrimidine²¹, 2,4-diamino-6-*p*-anisidino pyrimidine²¹ and 2,4-diamino-6-*p*-toluidino pyrimidine²²) was suspended in water (160 ml) to which glacial acetic acid was added drop by drop with stirring until a clear solution was obtained (ca 2–6 ml of glacial acetic acid was required). The solution was cooled in ice water and a cold solution of an equimolecular amount of the benzene diazonium chloride [prepared by adding a cold solution of sodium nitrite (0.004 mole) in water (4 ml) with stirring to an ice-cold solution of aniline (0.004 mole) in 1(*N*) hydrochloric acid (10 ml). Equivalent amounts of sodium nitrite and aniline were used in order to avoid excess of nitrous acid. The diazotized solution must contain excess of hydrochloric acid] was slowly added with stirring. The stirring was continued and after 5 min 2(*N*) sodium hydroxide solution was added drop by drop to bring the *pH* of the solution to 8–9, when a heavy coloured precipitate appeared. The stirring was then continued for four more hours. The mix-

ture was cooled in ice-water all through. The reaction mixture was kept in the refrigerator overnight. The crude product was filtered, washed several times with water, dried at 80° and then purified by crystallization.

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